

ON SOLVING QUADRATIC DIOPHANTINE EQUATION $15x^2 + y^2 = 4^n$

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Abstract:

Diophantine Equations named after ancient Greek mathematician Diophantus, plays a vital role not only in number theory but also in several branches of mathematics. In this paper, we have solved quadratic Diophantine equation $15x^2 + y^2 = 4^n$ and obtained its complete solutions.

Key Words: Quadratic Diophantine Equation, Integer solutions, Polar Form, Euler's Formula.**1. Introduction:**

Diophantine equations were equations whose solutions must be in integers. Since the solutions are integers and most often positive integers, such equations have more practical applications compared to other equations in mathematics. In this paper, we will solve quadratic Diophantine equation $15x^2 + y^2 = 4^n$ (1) using complex numbers.

2. Solving The Problem:

First, we observe that (1) has no solution in positive integers if $n = 1$, since in this case, the left hand side term $15x^2 + y^2 \geq 4$. So in the following method, we consider $n \geq 2$.

Now, we will find the polar form of $1 + i\sqrt{15}$

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + i\sqrt{15} &= r(\cos \theta + i \sin \theta) \\ \Rightarrow r \cos \theta &= 1, r \sin \theta = \sqrt{15} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

From this, we obtain $r^2 = 1 + 15 = 16$

$$\Rightarrow r = 4, \theta = \tan^{-1}(\sqrt{15}) \quad (3)$$

Hence the polar form of $(1 + i\sqrt{15})^{n-1}$ is given by

$$(1 + i\sqrt{15})^{n-1} = 4^{n-1} e^{i(n-1)\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{15})}$$

Now using Euler's formula, we obtain

$$(1 + i\sqrt{15})^{n-1} = 4^{n-1} \left(\cos \left((n-1)\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{15}) \right) + i \sin \left((n-1)\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{15}) \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

Assume that,

$$(y + i\sqrt{15}x) = 4^{1-\frac{n}{2}}(1 + i\sqrt{15})^{n-1} \quad (5)$$

$$(y - i\sqrt{15}x) = 4^{1-\frac{n}{2}}(1 - i\sqrt{15})^{n-1} \quad (6)$$

Now multiplying (5) & (6), we get,

$$y^2 + 15x^2 = 4^n$$

Which is (1).

Equating real & imaginary parts using (4) & (5), we get

$$x = \frac{4^{n/2}}{\sqrt{15}} \sin \left((n-1)\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{15}) \right) \quad (7)$$

$$y = 4^{n/2} \cos \left((n-1)\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{15}) \right) \quad (8)$$

Now from (7) and (8), if we consider $(|x|, |y|)$ then these pairs would provide positive integer solutions to the given Quadratic Diophantine Equation $15x^2 + y^2 = 4^n$.**3. Conclusion:**From (7) and (8), we observe that for $n \geq 2$, positive integer solutions to $15x^2 + y^2 = 4^n$ are given by

$$x = \frac{4^{n/2}}{\sqrt{15}} \left| \sin \left((n-1)\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{15}) \right) \right| \quad (9)$$

$$y = 4^{n/2} \left| \cos \left((n-1)\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{15}) \right) \right| \quad (10)$$

Thus for $n = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, \dots$ positive integer solutions (x, y) to $15x^2 + y^2 = 4^n$ are given by (1,1), (1,7), (3,11), (7,17), (5,61), (33,7), (13,251), (119,223), Thus the values of x and y from the above expression provides possible positive integer solutions to the given Quadratic Diophantine Equation $15x^2 + y^2 = 4^n$.

We can adopt similar methods to solve other type of Quadratic Diophantine equations using polar forms of suitable complex numbers.

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